

SOME INFORMATION ABOUT THE PREDATORY FELINES OF CENTRAL ASIA IN THE LITERATURE ON THE HISTORY OF THE ANCIENT WORLD.

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Anotatsiya: Our ideas about the ancient natural geography of Central Asia, especially its flora and fauna, are formed by the sources of ancient Greece, Iran, India, and China, as well as the information in the Zoroastrian holy book "Avesta". On the other hand, the archaeological research conducted in our country served to enrich the information in written sources. It can be seen that the information in the historical literature about the presence of feline predators such as lions, tigers, and leopards in the composition of the ancient fauna of Central Asia is in some cases interpreted in a mythical way. Since ancient times, all peoples have paid special attention to wild cats, believing that they are representatives of divine forces on earth. It is also believed that the wild cat is able to protect against various disasters and calamities. For these reasons, we can see that many images of wild cats have been preserved on rocks since the earliest times in our country. For example, in the images on the rocks of Sarmushsay; "Wild bulls, stags and deer with their antlers stuck around, mountain deer, deer, boar, wolf, leopard, dogs... are depicted[5,21]," writes academician A. Muhammadjanov. So, we can witness that the attitude towards wild felines in our country was reflected in rock paintings even in the Mesolithic period.

Keys words: Sarmushsay, Egypt, Mesopotamia, A. Muhammadjanov, Avesta, India, China, Khorezm, Amudarya.

In the course of the formation of class societies and states, it is observed that wild cats rise to the level of the sun, patron of rulers and even gods. It is even more noticeable in the worldview of the peoples of ancient Egypt, Mesopotamia, and India. It can be seen that a lion's head is depicted facing the rim of a pot on a handle of ceramic vessels found in Ancient Khorezm monuments dating back to the Kang state, or rather, the Early Kang period (IV-III centuries BC). Examples of such vessels are Jonboskala, Bozorkala, Qal'aliqir I-II, Kozaliqir, and most of them were found in Koyqirqalqal'a, the palace temple of the Khorezmshahs. The khum handle found in Khorezm's Jonbaskala is also characterized by a lion's head attached to its upper part, which seems to be biting the collar of the khum with its teeth. The Kal'aliqir II temple-fortress of the 5th century AD was designed to protect irrigation facilities and canals, and the well-known scientist Hamidulla Karomatov suggests that the bowls with lion heads found there served as totem amulets protecting against enemies[2, 154-155]. Based on the spread of the images of lions, wild cats in the archaeological and material monuments, the method of development and the order of use, scientists put forward the opinion that the imagination of wild cats and their protective function was widespread among the people in the IV-III centuries BC[1,23]. It can be seen that the image of lions is also reflected in the objects found in the Amudarya treasury, which are considered to belong to the 7th-3rd centuries BC in Central Asia. Hamidulla Karomatov notes that among the objects of the Amudarya treasure there is an image of a lion biting a golden hum, as well as images of a lion mauling a deer. The scientist analyzes information from historical literature and early religious ideas of the peoples of the Ancient East, and suggests that these images signaled the beginning of a new agricultural year[2, 125]. Also, among the items included in the "Treasure of Amudarya" there is an image of a leopard, which is one of the wild cats, and two breast badges are among the items, one of which depicts a tiger biting the fangs of its prey after killing an animal [8, 278]. This shows that the lion has been replaced by a tiger, the deer has been replaced by a deer, and the theme of new life or spring growth has not changed. Images of the tiger, which

is considered to be another of the wild cats, are found in many ancient monuments. H. In Karomatov's work "History of Mozaic Beliefs in Uzbekistan", it is mentioned that the image of a tiger attacking a camel was depicted on the bronze cover of a belt found in the Lavandak fortress of the Bukhara region and belonging to the IV-III centuries BC. Also, during the excavation of a burial mound near the village of Tavois in the Bukhara oasis, a belt buckle depicting a tiger attacking a camel was found in this monument. On the bronze ring of the belt found in this monument dating back to the 1st century BC, it is depicted that a tiger with its front legs on the neck of a camel with two humps kneeling on its front legs is biting its humpback, and the camel is biting the hind leg of the tiger. Based on the fact that such belts were widespread in Sogd until the 8th century and many were found in other cemeteries, scientists conclude that they were considered amulets with magical power[2, 125,163]. On the other hand, it can be concluded that the images made in the form of "Scythian animal style" in this science show the period and geography of the spread of this direction of art to settled areas.

The well-known scientist B.Ya. Stavisky also gave information: "Bronze rings found in Lavandak and Shakhrivayron monuments of Zarafshan oasis are elegantly made, the battle of a tiger and a camel with two scythes depicted in them is made in the "Animal style" of the nomads. [7, 160].

Information about wild predators of Central Asia was known in almost all countries of the ancient world. It is well known through archeological research conducted in Greece, as well as historical sources, that wild lions that are found in nature lived in ancient Greece in Thrace and Macedonia. Information about Central Asian lions in ancient Greece was known from the time of Alexander the Great's military campaigns. According to the information of Quintus Curtius Rufus, after conquering Samarkand, Alexander the Great went hunting here and hunted a lion of abnormal size. In the eighth book, the first chapter of the work "History of Alexander the Great", Quintus Curtius Rufus, in the land of the Sogdians, as the main symbol of wealth, the herd of wild animals kept in the areas of trees and green areas, wealth

is measured by the abundance or smallness of this herd, and the fact that several generations did not enter such places and hunt game animals. , because of the abundance of animals, Alexander organized a hunt in this grove, during the hunt, a lion attacked from a corner, Lysimachus, who was standing next to Alexander, when he wanted to kill him, the king did not allow him, and he wrote down that he himself killed him with one blow of a spear [3, 167]. Based on the information of Quintus Curtius Rufus, it is possible to conclude that the system of the first reserves of the ancient world was created to protect animals living in the wild in our country, to create an opportunity for them to reproduce freely.M. E. Based on Masson's information, the famous archaeologist scientist E. Rtveladze, in his encyclopedic reference Velikiy shelkovyy put ("The Great Silk Road"), cites the above-mentioned work of Quintus Curtius Rufus as the oldest written source for Central Asian lions. According to him, in 328 AD, Alexander of Macedonia organized a hunt and killed a lion in the Bazista region near Samarkand, which is called Paradiz[6,116]. In China, which is another large country of the ancient world, the first concepts about the lion appear around 300 BC. During this period, the novel "Mutuantszychjuan" appeared in China. In the work, the term lion is called "Swan'-nie". V.M., a well-known scientist who studied the history of cultural relations between ancient India and China. According to Stein, the term is derived from the Chinese pronunciation of the Sanskrit word "sinha" ("lion"). In the official Chinese sources, the ambassadors sent from Parthia to the Chinese emperor in 87 AD also mention that lions were brought to the territory of China for the first time and they were presented to the emperor as a gift [10,41]. In our opinion, lions were brought to China through Central Asia. Since China and India are geographically close countries, it was not possible to cross the Himalayas, the death of people and animals due to lack of air in the high mountains, the lack of development of sea navigation and the fact that the sea trade route between these countries was not opened is the basis for our conclusion. There is no information about the existence of these roads in the historical literature either. There are no further references to lions in the annals of

the Chinese Han Dynasty. Information about lions began to be cited in the source "Bei shi" ("History of Northern Houses"). In this source, we can see that lions live in the mountains south of Samarkand and are known as "Tashena", and lions are brought from these mountains to China as a tribute to the emperor[6,116]. There is information that tigers from Central Asian predatory cats (hereinafter referred to as "Turonian tiger") were taken to different countries of the world in ancient times. According to the information of the Internet source, Turanian tigers were also taken to the ancient Roman state. Tigers were brought from the territory of Iran and Armenia, which entered into political and economic relations with the Roman state earlier than from the regions of Central Asia. From the Turanian tigers, when the amphitheatres first tried to use them for gladiatorial combat, the gladiators voluntarily refused to take on this beast[12]. The fact that Turanian tigers lived longer than local lions, that written and zoological information about them is quite sufficient, that this type of tigers, their structure, are different from other species (seven types of tigers have been identified on Earth, they are Indian (Bengal), Turanian, Amur, Javan, It is known as South China, Bali, Sumatra, Indochina. Of these seven species, Turanian, Javan, Balinese tigers are extinct species [13]) we can think more widely about the differences. Turanian tigers differed from other species in having light yellow fur and slightly wider patterned tracks, as well as finer looking brown tracks. Habitats are mainly riverside reed beds, groves. Turanian tigers are widespread in Central Asia, Northern Iran, and the Caucasus. For this reason, we can see that it is sometimes called the Caucasian or Caspian tiger. There are different opinions about the etymology of the term tiger, the first one is the stripes on it, and the second one is that it is a term used in relation to the appearance of a tiger hundreds or even thousands of km away from its habitat. It has been determined that a tiger can cover a distance of 100 km in one day [14]. Due to the fact that Turanian tigers were preserved until the middle of the 20th century, there are clear ideas and concepts about their weight, body and tail length, as well as the areas where they lived in our country. In the national encyclopedia of the Republic of Uzbekistan,

about the Turan tigers, one of the seven younger generations of the largest representative of the feline family (body length - 160-290 cm, 3 m, tail length - 114 cm, weight up to 290 kg) is the Turan tiger. , until the 1950s, it was found in riverside swamps and reed beds in the lower reaches of the Amudarya [11,360]. Subspecies of tigers included in the international red book (unfortunately extinct) are presented. The leopard is one of the predatory felines that lived in Central Asia, and its image is known from prehistoric rock paintings, as well as from ancient, medieval monuments in Central Asia. The first written information about Central Asian leopards, their habitats, can be found in Chinese sources. The annals of the Tang Dynasty contain information about leopards brought from Central Asia as gifts to the imperial court. In the work "Sin Tan Shu" ("The New History of the Tang Dynasty"), it is written that the unique leopards of Central Asia live in the territory of the current state of Tokharistan (Kedolo), the capital of this country is Sychutjian (the city of Sychutjian in the geographical tracts of the Tang period is called Gudoshi, Kedolo, Tukhulo (Tokharistan in Chinese sources at different times [4,281]) is mentioned as the capital of the state. T. Fujita, a well-known Japanese scholar engaged in the etymology of the name of this city, suggests that the name of the city of Si Kandah, which is mentioned in the medieval Arab sources in Tokharistan, is named in the Chinese historical literature) is the city of the Kai-yuan era. In the year 17 (03.02.729-22.01.730), it is possible to read the information about the arrival of ambassadors from this country to the imperial palace, among the gifts brought by the ambassadors were red leopards with black spots[4,87].

According to the information of the well-known scientist E. Shefer, the cities of Maymurg, Kesh, Bukhara, Samarkand in Central Asia are mentioned in Chinese sources of the 8th century as places where leopards were imported. According to the information of E. Shefer, leopards were among the gifts brought to the emperor from Samarkand in 713, and hawks, falcons, dogs and leopards were brought to the palace of Emperor Su-zun in 762. Analyzing the chronicles of E. Shefer Tan period, one can read the information related to the fact that leopards were brought from Central

Asia to China mainly for hunting, and kept as exotic animals in the homes of palace officials and noblemen[9,124].

Well-known archaeologist scientist E. Retveladze in his "Encyclopedic reference of the Great Silk Road" repeats the opinions of E. Schaefer cited above, regarding the fact that wild cats like dogs, leopards, and cheetahs brought from Central Asia to China were mainly used for hunting[6,115].

In short, lions, tigers, leopards, and cheetahs, which are the wild cats of Central Asia, have lived in this region since primitive times. Predatory cats are distinguished by their adaptation to a specific climate in the local fauna, their ability to live in harsh climatic conditions. These ideas are expressed in the early sources that provide information about Central Asian predatory cats. It is often mentioned in the historical literature that Central Asian wild cats were taken for various purposes in the large countries of the ancient world, such as Rome and China. We currently do not have complete, accurate summaries of the sizes of some of the big cats (with the exception of Turanian tigers) from the information provided in the historical literature. We believe that lions, leopards, and cheetahs living in the Turan region are a separate local species, and we believe that studying and analyzing their differences from other species in the world is one of the future tasks.

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